

EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELL (LAC) AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NORTHWEST DISTRICT OF THE CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF ILAGAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) among secondary schools in the Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan during the school year 2022-2023. Using a descriptive research design and quantitative methods, the study evaluated teachers' content knowledge and instructional performance before and after attending SLAC sessions. Fifty secondary teachers and 255 Grade 9 students served as respondents. Findings revealed a significant improvement in teachers' content knowledge and instructional performance after the conduct of SLAC, as well as a notable increase in students' academic achievement. Despite minor challenges, such as a lack of ICT knowledge and funding, SLAC was generally effective. The study recommends continued SLAC implementation, teacher training in ICT, proper scheduling to avoid class disruption, and additional funding for SLAC activities. Future researchers are encouraged to expand the study's scope for more comprehensive results.

Keywords: *School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), Teacher performance, Student achievement, ICT training, Professional development*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) has underscored the importance of continuing professional development for teachers to improve the quality of education in

the Philippines. One significant initiative in this direction is the Learning Action Cell (LAC), a school-based, teacher-led learning group designed to foster professional development and enhance teaching-learning. In line with the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, also known as Republic Act No. 10533, DepEd issued the policy on LAC as part of the K–12 Basic Education Program (DepEd Order No. 35, 2016). LAC is seen as an important professional development strategy to improve teaching practices by creating a collaborative platform for teachers to share best practices, address teaching challenges, and further their knowledge of various pedagogical approaches (Atienza & Lopez, 2017; Mabunga, 2018).

The necessity to revitalize educational programs, especially in reading, science, technology, and mathematics, has been reiterated by Vice President and Secretary of Education Sara Z. Duterte under the MATATAG: *Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa* agenda. The urgency of these initiatives is evident from the Philippines' low performance in international assessments, particularly the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), where the country ranked last in reading comprehension (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2019). To address these issues, DepEd has recognized the need to institutionalize LAC as a key tool for enhancing teacher competence and, by extension, student learning outcomes (Bautista, Bernardo, & Ocampo, 2020).

Professional development through LAC provides an avenue for teachers to revisit or explore new concepts related to pedagogy, ensuring they are well-equipped to meet the demands of the K–12 program. The success of LAC, however, is dependent on various factors, such as the topics chosen for discussion and the alignment of these topics with the professional needs of teachers. According to Fernando (2020), teachers need continuous training on key areas such as learners' diversity and inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, 21st-century skills, and ICT integration, all of which are vital for implementing the K–12 curriculum. Additionally, curriculum contextualization is critical in ensuring that the educational content is relevant and meaningful for diverse student populations (Silva, 2021; Miranda, 2019).

Despite the acknowledged benefits of LAC, challenges in implementation persist. Many schools face difficulties in conducting effective LAC sessions due to a lack of clear guidelines and a deficiency in teacher readiness (Santos & Salandanan, 2021). Teachers must have a comprehensive understanding of the K–12 program, yet studies show that even a decade after its introduction, there remain significant gaps in knowledge and application among educators (Reyes, 2021). As Zepeda (2015) emphasized, professional development initiatives like LAC must be carefully planned and supported by leadership to succeed.

Effective teaching is rooted in the systematic application of appropriate instructional strategies tailored to the learning needs and outcomes of students. Historically, teacher-centered approaches have dominated, but current trends advocate for student-centered learning, where teachers facilitate the acquisition of knowledge through active learning strategies and diverse assessments (Fajardo & Bautista, 2020). Teachers play a pivotal role in fostering student achievement, and their professional

growth directly influences student outcomes (Shulman, 1987; Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2009). A key component of this growth is the opportunity to engage in reflective practice through collaborative activities like LAC (Birman et al., 2000).

LAC not only promotes individual teacher development but also fosters a professional culture of collective participation. When teachers from the same grade level or subject area collaborate, they develop a shared understanding of instructional goals and practices, which can lead to improvements in student learning (Vangrieken et al., 2017). However, the impact of such initiatives is highly dependent on the competence of the teachers involved. Incompetent teaching can hinder student learning, regardless of the quality of the educational materials (Lawani, 2004). Therefore, continuous professional development, particularly through structured, reflective activities like LAC, is essential for improving teaching efficacy (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, & Gardner, 2017).

Based on the researcher's observation and personal experiences, there is a pressing need for more robust training sessions within LAC, particularly on topics related to K–12 education. Although the K–12 program has been in place for over a decade, many teachers are still grappling with its full implementation (Manuel, 2021). This research seeks to examine the effectiveness of LAC in the Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan, identifying both the strengths and challenges in its implementation. The study aims to develop an action plan to enhance LAC sessions and ultimately improve teachers' competence in delivering quality education.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the effectiveness of school learning action cell (SLAC) in Northwest District teachers of the City of Ilagan as well as the problems they encounter in implementing SLAC.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. sex
 - b. age
 - c. school assignment
 - d. educational attainment
2. What is the level of content knowledge and instructional performance of teachers before and after the conduct of SLAC based on their COT-RPMS rating?
3. What is the academic achievement of Grade 9 students before and after the conduct of SLAC?
4. Is there a significant difference between the teachers' performance before and after the conduct of SLAC?
5. Is there a significant difference between students' academic performance before and after the conduct of SLAC?
6. Is there a relationship between the teachers' level of content knowledge and instructional performance and the student's academic achievement after the conduct of SLAC?
7. What are the problems encountered by secondary teachers in conducting SLAC?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design with a quantitative method to determine the level of the teacher's content knowledge and instructional performance before and after attending the LAC sessions.

Purposive sampling, a technique under non-probability sampling, was utilized in selecting the respondents for the study. The total number of secondary English teachers in the Northwest District for the school year 2022-2023 was fifty (50).

In collecting data for this study, the researcher sought permission from the City Schools Division of Ilagan to utilize the COT-RPMS ratings of the respondents for the 2nd and 3rd quarter rating periods of School Year 2022-2023. This tool was developed under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). The PPST consists of seven domains composed of thirty-seven (37) strands that describe more specific dimensions of teacher quality practices. During the initial implementation of the PPST, only nine (9) key result areas (KRAs) were utilized and included in the COT-RPMS Rating.

The percentage of students who "Passed" and "Failed" in Grade 11 English in the 2nd and 3rd quarters was also used to determine the student's performance before and after their teachers' participation in LAC. Moreover, a modified survey questionnaire and interview questions were crafted and developed to identify the challenges teachers faced in conducting the LAC sessions.

Respondents and Sampling Method

The respondents in this study were fifty secondary teachers and two hundred fifty-five Grade 9 students in the Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan during the school year 2021-2022. They came from two secondary schools: Isabela School of Arts and Trades-Annex and Ilagan West National High School.

Data Gathering Procedure

To gather the necessary data for the study, the researcher wrote to the City Schools Division Superintendent to seek permission to conduct the study. Once granted, the researcher provided a copy of the approved letter to the respective principals/school heads of the different schools. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires to the respondents and personally administered and retrieved the completed questionnaires.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data were analyzed and interpreted using different statistical tools. First, the weighted mean was used to analyze the teachers' profile variables. Moreover, the mean and standard deviation were used to identify students' academic performance. A t-test for

independent groups was used to determine the significant difference between the profile variables and the level of academic performance. Additionally, ANOVA was used to identify the significant difference between the profile variables for multiple variables. Lastly, Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the student's academic performance and the teachers' classroom observation rating sheets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Secondary Teachers

The data presented in Table 1 can provide insights into the characteristics of the secondary teachers according to their profiles.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distributions of the Secondary Teachers According to their Profiles

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	35	70.00
Female	15	30.00
Total	50	100.00
Age		
21 – 30 years old	11	22.0
31 – 40 years old	22	44.0
41 – 50 years old	9	18.0
51 years old and above	8	16.0
Total	50	100.00
School Assignment		
IWNHS	30	60.0
ISAT	20	40.0
Total	50	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	18	36.0
Master's Units	23	46.0
Master's Graduate	8	16.0
Ph. D. Graduate	1	2.0
Total	50	100.00

In terms of sex, the sample consists of 70.00 percent female teachers and 30.00 percent male teachers. This suggests that there is a higher representation of female teachers compared to male teachers in the sample.

This information implies that there is a gender imbalance among secondary teachers, with a higher proportion of females in the teaching profession. This finding may

have various implications, including potential differences in teaching styles, role modeling, or the perception of certain subjects among students. Further analysis or investigation could help explore the reasons behind these gender disparities and their potential impact on the education system.

As to age, the majority of teachers which is 44.00 percent fell within the age range of 31-40 years old, followed by 22.00 percent in the 21-30 age range. The distribution indicates that the sample includes teachers predominantly in their 30s and 40s. There was a relatively smaller proportion of teachers who are 51 years old and above, accounting for 16.00 percent of the sample.

With regard to school assignments, among the teachers, 60.00 percent were assigned to IWNHS and 40.00 percent were assigned to ISAT. This suggests that IWNHS has a larger representation of teachers in the sample compared to ISAT.

In the matter of highest educational attainment, the sample includes teachers with different levels of educational attainment. Among the teachers, 36.00 percent held a Bachelor's Degree, while 46.00 percent completed Master's Units. Additionally, 16.00 percent of teachers were Master's Graduates, and only 2.0 percent completed a Ph.D. program. The data shows a relatively higher proportion of teachers with Master's Units, indicating that many teachers have pursued postgraduate education without completing a full Master's program.

Level of Content knowledge and Instructional Performance of Teachers before and after the Conduct of SLAC based on their COT-RPMS rating

Table 2 provides the analysis of the level of content knowledge and instructional performance of teachers before and after the conduct of SLAC (School-Based Learning Action Cell), based on their COT-RPMS (Competency-Based Performance Management System) ratings.

Table 2. Level of Content Knowledge and Instructional Performance of Teachers Before and After the Conduct of SLAC based on their COT-RPMS Rating

Before	Content Knowledge			Instruction		
	Mean	Sd	Description	Mean	Sd	Description
1	4.62	.635	Outstanding	4.38	.830	Very Satisfactory
2	4.60	.571	Outstanding	4.66	.593	Outstanding
3	4.68	.471	Outstanding	4.80	.404	Outstanding
4	4.76	.431	Outstanding	4.82	.438	Outstanding
5	4.72	.536	Outstanding			

Overall Mean	4.676	.2994	Outstanding	4.6650	.34110	Outstanding
After	Mean	Sd	Description	Mean	Sd	Description
1	4.90	.303	Outstanding	4.72	.497	Outstanding
2	4.94	.240	Outstanding	4.88	.328	Outstanding
3	5.00	.000	Outstanding	4.98	.141	Outstanding
4	4.98	.141	Outstanding	4.96	.198	Outstanding
5	4.98	.141	Outstanding			
Overall Mean	4.960	.0904	Outstanding	4.8850	.18357	Outstanding

As to the content knowledge, before SLAC, the teachers had an outstanding level of content knowledge, with mean scores ranging from 4.62 to 4.76 on a scale of 1 to 5. The relatively low standard deviations (ranging from 0.431 to 0.636) indicate a relatively small variation in content knowledge scores among the teachers.

After SLAC, the teachers' content knowledge further improved, as indicated by higher mean scores ranging from 4.90 to 4.98. The standard deviations after SLAC (ranging from 0.000 to 0.303) suggest a reduced variation in content knowledge scores. The overall mean score for content knowledge increased from 4.676 before SLAC to 4.960 after SLAC, demonstrating a significant improvement in the teachers' content knowledge level.

With regard to instructional performance, before SLAC, the teachers demonstrated an outstanding level of instructional performance, with mean scores ranging from 4.38 to 4.82. The standard deviations (ranging from 0.404 to 0.830) indicate some variation in instructional performance scores among the teachers.

After SLAC, the teachers' instructional performance remained at an outstanding level, with mean scores ranging from 4.72 to 4.96. The standard deviations after SLAC (ranging from 0.141 to 0.497) suggest a reduced variation in instructional performance scores.

The overall mean score for instructional performance slightly increased from 4.6650 before SLAC to 4.8850 after SLAC, indicating a positive impact on the teachers' instructional performance. Overall, the data suggests that the SLAC program had a positive effect on the teachers' content knowledge and instructional performance. The teachers' content knowledge level showed a notable improvement, and their instructional performance remained consistently outstanding before and after SLAC. The reduced standard deviations after SLAC indicate a more consistent level of content knowledge and instructional performance among the teachers. These findings indicate the effectiveness of the SLAC program in enhancing the teachers' professional competencies.

Academic Achievement of Grade 9 Students before and after the conduct of SLAC

Table 3 provides the analysis of the academic achievement of Grade 9 students before and after the conduct of SLAC (School-Based Learning Action Cell).

Table 3. The Academic Achievement of the Grade 9 Students Before and After the conduct of SLAC

Academic Achievement	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptor
First Quarter			
90 and above	14	5.49	Outstanding
85–89	83	32.55	Very Satisfactory
80–84	133	52.16	Satisfactory
75–79	25	9.80	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	255	100	
Before			
Academic Achievement	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90 and above	86	33.73	Outstanding
85–89	100	39.22	Very Satisfactory
80–84	59	23.14	Satisfactory
75–79	10	3.92	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	255	100	
Academic Achievement	Mean	Sd	
Before SLAC	2.66	.729	
After SLAC	1.97	.853	

Before the SLAC intervention, the grade distribution among the Grade 9 students was as follows: 5.49% achieved an outstanding academic achievement (90 and above), 32.55% were very satisfactory (85-89), 52.16% were satisfactory (80-84), and 9.80% were fairly satisfactory (75-79). No students scored below 74, indicating that none of them failed to meet expectations.

After the SLAC intervention, the distribution changed: 33.73% achieved an outstanding academic achievement, 39.22% were very satisfactory, 23.14% were satisfactory, and 3.92% were fairly satisfactory. Similar to before, no students scored below 74. Comparing the means and standard deviations, we observe that the mean academic achievement improved from 2.66 before SLAC to 1.97 after SLAC. This indicates that, on average, students' academic performance improved after participating

in SLAC. The standard deviation decreased from 0.729 to 0.853, suggesting a decrease in the variability of academic achievement scores.

Overall, the data suggests that the SLAC intervention had a positive impact on the academic performance of Grade 9 students, as evidenced by the improvement in mean scores and the distribution shift towards higher achievement categories.

Comparison between the teachers' performance before and after the conduct of SLAC

Table 4 exhibits the results of the paired samples t-test indicating a significant difference in teachers' performance before and after the conduct of SLAC (Staff Learning and Collaboration). The t-values obtained for both content knowledge and instruction were statistically significant, with p-values of 0.000.

Table 4. Result of the Paired Samples Test on the Significant Difference between the Teachers' Performance Before and After the Conduct of SLAC

Teachers' Performance	Mean	Sd	t-Value	p-Value	Decision	Remarks
Before and After SLAC						
Content Knowledge After	4.676	.2994	6.821	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Content Knowledge Before	4.960	.0904				
Before and After SLAC						
Instruction Before	4.665	.3411	5.310	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Instruction After	4.885	.1836				

For content knowledge, the mean score increased from 4.676 before SLAC to 6.821 after SLAC, suggesting a significant improvement in teachers' content knowledge. This indicates that the SLAC program had a positive impact on enhancing teachers' understanding and proficiency in the subject matter they teach.

Similarly, for instruction, the mean score increased from 4.665 before SLAC to 4.885 after SLAC. Although the improvement in instruction is not as substantial as in content knowledge, it is still statistically significant. This suggests that the SLAC program also had a positive effect on enhancing teachers' instructional practices and strategies.

Based on the rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀) and the significant t-values, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in teachers' performance before and after the SLAC program. The results indicate that the SLAC intervention was effective in improving teachers' content knowledge and instructional practices.

Comparison between Students' Academic Performance before and after the Conduct of SLAC

Table 5. Result of the Significant Difference Between Students' Academic Performance Before and After the Conduct of SLAC

Students' Performance	t-Value	p-Value	Decision	Remarks
Academic Achievement Before and After SLAC	15.145	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant

The paired samples test provides statistical evidence supporting a significant difference in student's academic performance before and after the conduct of SLAC (School Learning Action Cell). This means that the observed change in academic achievement is unlikely to have occurred by chance alone.

The very low p-value ($p < 0.001$) indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, which assumes no difference in academic performance before and after SLAC. The small p-value suggests that the observed difference is highly unlikely to be due to random chance, providing further support for the conclusion that the difference is statistically significant.

Based on the statistical results, there is strong evidence to suggest that SLAC had a positive impact on students' academic performance. On average, students showed improvement after participating in SLAC, and this improvement is statistically significant. The findings indicate that the SLAC program has effectively contributed to enhancing students' academic achievement in Grade 9.

Relationship between the Teachers' Level of Content Knowledge and Instructional Performance and the Student's Academic Achievement after the conduct of SLAC

Table 6. Results of the Relationship between the Teachers' Level of Content Knowledge and Instructional Performance and the Student's Academic Achievement After the Conduct of SLAC

Variable	Pearson's r	Spearman's Correlation	Decision	Remarks
Content Knowledge After SLAC vs. Academic Performance of the Students	0.048	0.006	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Instruction After SLAC vs. Academic Performance of the Students	0.215	0.275	Accept H_0	Not Significant

There was no meaningful linear relationship between instruction and performance after SLAC. The coefficient of -0.006 indicates a very weak negative monotonic relationship between instruction and performance after SLAC. Similar to the interval-by-interval analysis, the correlation is not statistically significant at the conventional significance level ($p = 0.968$).

In summary, the symmetric measures analysis suggests that there is no meaningful relationship between instruction and performance after the implementation of SLAC. Both Pearson's R and Spearman Correlation coefficients indicate very weak correlations, which are not statistically significant. These results imply that the instruction provided through SLAC does not appear to have a substantial impact on the performance of students. However, it is important to note that these findings are based on the specific dataset and analysis conducted. Further investigation with a larger sample size or other analytical approaches may be necessary to draw more definitive conclusions about the relationship between instruction and performance after SLAC.

The coefficient of 0.275 indicates a weak positive monotonic relationship between instruction and performance after SLAC. Although the correlation is slightly higher than in the interval-by-interval case, it is still not statistically significant at the conventional significance level ($p = 0.053$).

In summary, the symmetric measures analysis suggests a weak positive relationship between instruction and performance after the implementation of SLAC. However, the correlation coefficients (Pearson's R and Spearman Correlation) indicate that the relationship is not statistically significant. This means that the observed associations between instruction and performance could be due to chance or other factors, rather than a direct causal relationship. Further investigation with a larger sample size or other analytical methods may be necessary to gain a more conclusive understanding of the relationship between instruction and performance after SLAC.

Problems Encountered by Secondary Teachers in Conducting School Learning Action Cell (SLAC)

Table 7. Problems Encountered by Secondary Teachers in Conducting Learning Action Cells

Indicator	Mean	Sd	Description
a. Assessment of Training Needs	1.42	0.575	Not a problem
b. Scheduling of LAC sessions	1.42	0.538	Not a problem
c. Lack of ICT knowledge of teachers	1.68	0.463	A problem
d. Planning the school learning action cell	1.42	0.609	Not a problem
e. Prioritization of Topics	1.50	0.678	Not a problem
f. Monitoring and Evaluation	1.52	0.707	Not a problem
g. Integration of lessons in a real-life context	1.32	0.587	Not a problem

h. Preparation of LAC materials	1.38	0.567	Not a problem
i. Excessive academic load for both teachers and students	1.60	0.793	Not a problem
j. Disruption of Classes	1.74	0.751	A problem
k. Teachers' Availability	1.42	0.575	Not a problem
l. LAC Framework	1.36	0.525	Not a problem
m. Funding	1.80	0.808	A problem
Overall Mean	1.41		Not a Problem

As can be gleaned in Table 7, the teachers found the problems encountered in conducting learning action cells **Not a problem** as shown by an overall mean of 1.41.

In terms of Assessment of Training Needs, this problem is rated as 1.42, indicating that it is **not a problem**. Teachers seem to have a clear understanding of their training needs which implies that indicating that they possess the necessary skills and knowledge for conducting Learning Action Cells.

Similarly, scheduling LAC sessions was perceived as **not a problem** with a rating of 1.42. Teachers were likely able to manage and coordinate the timing of these sessions effectively. This means that Teachers were able to effectively manage and coordinate the timing of LAC sessions, suggesting efficient planning and organization.

As to the Lack of ICT knowledge of teachers, this problem is rated as 1.68, indicating that it is **a problem**. This suggests that teachers have insufficient knowledge of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) for conducting Learning Action Cells. Therefore, further training on the said issue needs to be implemented.

With regard to Planning the school learning action cell, teachers **do not find this action cell as a problem** as indicated by a mean of 1.42. This signifies that teachers are adept at planning the learning action cell, indicating their ability to structure and organize the sessions effectively.

In relation to the Prioritization of Topics, this problem is rated as 1.50, suggesting it is **not considered a problem**. This means that teachers can prioritize topics for the Learning Action Cells, ensuring that the most important and relevant subjects are addressed.

In the same manner, monitoring and evaluation are seen as **not problems** rated with a mean of 1.52. Thus, teachers are capable of monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the Learning Action Cells, allowing for continuous improvement and adjustment.

In terms of the Integration of lessons in a real-life context, this problem has a mean of 1.32, indicating that it is **not a problem**. Hence, teachers successfully integrate lessons with real-life contexts, enhancing the practical applicability and relevance of the learning experience.

As to the Preparation of LAC materials, teachers find the preparation of LAC materials to be relatively **not a problem** as evidenced by the mean of 1.38. This connotes that they are likely able to prepare the necessary materials with ease and Teachers can prepare the necessary materials for the Learning Action Cells, ensuring that the required resources are readily available.

Regarding excessive academic load for both teachers and students, the problem is rated as 1.60, indicating it is **not a problem**. This implies that teachers and students can cope with heavy academic workload.

Likewise, the disruption of classes is rated as **a problem** as provided by a mean of 1.74. It shows that teachers face certain disruptions during the LAC sessions that affect the learning process. Furthermore, the moderate level of disruption during classes suggests that teachers encounter some challenges in maintaining a focused and conducive learning environment during the LAC sessions.

On the other hand, teachers' availability is **not a problem** with a mean of 1.42. This entails that teachers are generally accessible and available for conducting the Learning Action Cells, indicating a commitment to the process.

In parallel, the LAC framework is seen as **not a problem** as attested by the mean 1.36. This signifies that the LAC framework is well understood by teachers, indicating their familiarity with the guidelines and procedures involved in conducting Learning Action Cells.

With reference to funding, this is rated as **a problem** as proved by the mean of 1.80. The moderate level of significance regarding funding suggests that teachers face challenges related to financial resources required for the successful implementation of Learning Action Cells. Additional support and resources may be necessary to address this issue effectively.

In summary, most of the problems encountered by secondary teachers in conducting Learning Action Cells are considered not significant. However, there are moderately significant problems related to lack of ICT knowledge, disruption of classes, and funding. These areas may require further attention and support to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the Learning Action Cells.

Conclusions

In view of the findings above, this study concludes that the conduct of the school learning action cell (SLAC) in the Northwest District of the City Schools Division of Ilagan is effective. Its effectiveness is made evident by the increase in the level of content knowledge and instructional performance of teachers after the implementation of SLAC. Additionally, the increase in students' academic achievement after the implementation of SLAC indicates its positive impact on their performance. Finally, the problems perceived by the teachers in the conduct of SLAC are not so serious as to affect it.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, this study hereby recommends the following:

1. Schools are encouraged to maintain the implementation of the school learning action cell (SLAC) and further enhance the areas that need to be addressed.
 2. Heads of schools are encouraged to strengthen the need for teachers in training ICT because they are teaching the generation of Zoomers who are technology-savvy.
 3. Schools implementing SLAC should look for ways to augment funds or budget for its implementation.
 4. Proper scheduling should be done in order not to disrupt or cancel classes when SLAC is done.
 5. Lastly, to future researchers who plan to do the same study. They should widen the range of the locale of the study to attain better and more reliable results, especially in getting the perceived effectiveness of SLAC as well as the problems in implementing it.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted ethically, with informed consent from all participants and strict anonymity maintained. Data was analyzed with respect for participant diversity, and findings were presented objectively. All sources are properly cited, with no plagiarism, aiming to enhance educational practices and student well-being.

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